

1 **A role for DcR2 (*TNFRSF10D*), a death domain-containing decoy receptor for TNF family member**
2 **TRAIL, in triple negative breast cancer.**

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7 We describe here functional significance of expression of a death receptor of the TNF superfamily, DcR2,
8 encoded by *TNFRSF10D* in triple negative breast cancer. We discovered *TNFRSF10D* as a regulator of
9 disease outcome through tumor methylome analysis in humans with TNBC which identified positions in
10 the genome whose differential methylation was most significantly correlated with decreased time to death.
11 In a large cohort of humans with breast cancer, *TNFRSF10D* messenger RNA tumor expression was a
12 significant correlate of and negative indicator of overall survival in basal subtype breast cancer and only in
13 the basal subtype. *TNFRSF10D*, a component gene of the senescence program, was co-regulated with
14 genes that have cardinal functions in transformation, including EGFR, MET, and BMP, molecules that
15 function in growth factor signaling in cancer and stem cells including ERBB2, CSF1, OSMR and LIF,
16 ATP-binding cassette ABCC2 and ABCC3, steroid hormone metabolism genes DHRS3 and HSD3B7,
17 hepatocyte nuclear factors HNF1A and HNF4A, cell death effector BCL3, and with regulators of cell cycle
18 progression, including CDKN1A. The data support a role for death receptor signaling in disease
19 progression in hormone receptor negative (basal subtype or triple negative) breast cancer.

20 **References**

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